

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *CLEOME VISCOSA*, LINN. PART I THE CONSTITUENTS.

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A new unsaturated acid, $C_{27}H_{50}O_3$ named viscous acid and a new flavone, $C_{15}H_{10}O_2(OH)_2(OMe)$, named viscosin have been isolated from the seeds of *Cleome viscosa*. Tannins, reducing sugars, and myristic and palmitic acids have also been detected.

Cleome viscosa, Linn. (N.O. Capparidæ) which is called Hurhur or Hulhul or Kanphute in Hindusthani, Hurhuriya in Bengali, is a common plant found throughout tropical India, Ceylon and other warmer climates and has been long in use in India as a domestic remedy. According to Moodeen Sheriff, the seeds are anthelmintic, rubeficient and vesicant and in this respect they are regarded much superior to the mustard seeds and equal to the European mustard. According to O'Shaughnessy the whole plant is used in counter-irritation and blistering in Cochin China (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants," 1918, I, 98). In the United States, the roots are said to be used as a vermifuge. According to Lindley the seeds are given occasionally in fevers and diarrhoea.

Cleome pentaphylla has been the subject of a previous investigation (Misra and Dutt, *Proc. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 3, 45), but nothing is known regarding the constituents of *C. Viscosa*.*

From the benzene extract of the seeds of *C. Viscosa* we have been able to isolate a fixed oil (36.59%) which on standing deposited some crystalline matter, and this has been found to be a mixture of myristic acid, palmitic acid and a new acid, *viscous acid*. From the alcoholic extract of the seeds a new flavone, called by the authors "*viscosin*" (yield 0.04%), tannins, reducing sugars, as also viscous acid have been isolated. Viscous acid, m.p. 97°, seems to be an unsaturated fatty acid having the molecular formula, $C_{27}H_{50}O_3$. Although it does not decompose bicarbonate, it can be titrated with caustic potash solution in alcohol and turns blue litmus red in alcoholic medium. It decolourises bromine in chloroform, but attempts to prepare a crystalline bromo derivative have failed. Oxidation with cold dilute potassium permanganate solution yielded a dihydroxy acid, $C_{27}H_{54}O_5$, and obviously it contains one double bond. It has got an iodine value of 22.5 (Wijis' method).

* These two species of cleome are known in Hindusthani by the same name "Hurhur", and they are much confused one with the other in local markets,

Viscosin, m.p. 294-95° (decomp.), has the molecular formula $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$ and contains no water of crystallisation. A preliminary examination readily reveals its nature as a colouring matter belonging to the flavone group. It gives a dark green colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and forms a triacetyl derivative. It contains one methoxy group. These facts indicate that viscosin is a monomethoxytrihydroxyflavone, which is stable to atmospheric oxidation in alkaline solution. An alcoholic solution of viscosin (1%) was found to have a well-defined absorption band between wave-length 4100 and 4620 Å, having the absorption maximum at 4425 Å.

A thorough and detailed study of the physiological action of viscosin with special reference to anthelmintic properties will be undertaken at the School of Tropical Medicine, Calcutta. Further work on the subject is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

An authentic sample of the seeds of *Cleome viscosa* was obtained from the Punjab, dried in shade and was crushed to a fine powder. When burnt completely it left 7-10% of a dirty white ash consisting of 13.33% of water-soluble and 86.67% of water-insoluble inorganic material. Besides silica the following ions were detected in the ash: K, Fe, Ca, Mg, Cl, SO_4 , PO_4 , CO_3 .

In order to form an idea of the percentage and nature of the soluble portions of the drug, a sample of the dried and crushed seeds (25 g.) was successively extracted with various solvents in a Soxhlet's apparatus, when the following amounts of extract dried at 100° were obtained.

Benzene Extract (36.59%).—A reddish yellow oil was obtained from which some waxy material separated.

Alcoholic Extract (2.15%).—A yellowish brown mass was obtained, which is soluble in alkalis with light yellow colour. It gave a dark green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and reduced Fehling's solution and gave a flocculent precipitate with alcoholic lead acetate.

Chloroform Extract (0.6%) and *Acetone extract* (0.24%) were brown and gave ferric chloride reaction and a yellow flocculent precipitate with alcoholic lead acetate as well as with basic lead acetate.

The powdered material (4.2 kg.) was repeatedly extracted with benzene, till a portion of it was found to leave no oily residue on complete removal of the solvent. The reddish yellow oil (800 g.) on standing deposited

some dirty white crystalline matter (A) which was filtered, washed well with benzene, dried and then taken up with ether. The fraction, insoluble in ether, was crystallised twice from ethyl alcohol and then repeatedly from methyl alcohol when white needles of viscous acid melting sharply at 97° were obtained (yield, 0.1%). Viscous acid is soluble in ethyl and methyl alcohols, acetone, ethyl acetate, easily so in chloroform and benzene and insoluble in ether and water. It does not reduce Fehling's solution. It dissolves in cold concentrated sulphuric acid, gives no colour with ferric chloride and does not form oxime or acetyl derivatives. [Found: C, 76.31, 76.26; H, 12.32, 12.50. M.W. (from lead salt), 437; Equiv., 442. $C_{27}H_{32}O_3$ requires C, 76.41; H, 12.26 per cent. M.W. 424; Equiv., 424].

Sodium Salt.—The neutralised solution of the acid when concentrated to about 30 c.c. and when left overnight deposited the sodium salt as white needles which, when recrystallised from alcohol, melted at $129-30^{\circ}$. It is insoluble in water.

Lead Salt.—The acid (1 g.) was dissolved in hot alcohol and an alcoholic solution of lead acetate was added drop by drop when a flocculent white precipitate was obtained which was collected and recrystallised from isoamyl alcohol in white crystalline powder, m.p. 138° . It is easily soluble in pyridine, amyl and isoamyl alcohols and less so in ethyl and methyl alcohols, insoluble in acetone, benzene and ethyl acetate. [Found: Pb, 20.04, 19.85. $(C_{27}H_{31}O_3)_2$ Pb requires Pb, 19.66 per cent].

Oxidation of Viscous Acid.—Viscous acid (1 g.) was suspended in 100 c.c. of caustic potash solution (5%) and a dilute solution (2%) of potassium permanganate was added slowly followed by vigorous shaking till it was in slight excess and left overnight. The precipitated manganese dioxide was dissolved by passing a current of sulphur dioxide, the insoluble white precipitate filtered and dried and extracted by hot alcohol repeatedly. The insoluble precipitate was of unchanged viscous acid. The soluble portion was crystallised from methyl alcohol and finally from ethyl acetate. The yield of the hydroxy acid was poor but when the oxidation was carried out in pyridine solution the yield improved. It melted at 127° . (Found: C, 70.69; H, 11.58. $C_{27}H_{34}O_5$ requires C, 70.74; H, 11.79 per cent).

Isolation of Myristic and Palmitic Acids.—The ether-soluble portion of the crystalline matter (A) on concentration deposited a brown substance which was purified by boiling with animal charcoal in methyl alcohol and after recrystallisation from the same medium, it was obtained in the form of white waxy crystals (6.2 g.), m.p. 48° (yield 0.15%). It was acidic towards litmus. Fractionally crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and water for a

number of times, it was separated into two fractions having constant melting points of 54° and 62° respectively, which remained undepressed when mixed melting points were taken with authentic specimens of myristic and palmitic acids.

The first fraction gave the following analytical data, which are in agreement with those of myristic acid. [Found: C, 73.42, 73.61; H, 12.04, 12.13. M. W., 240 (by titration). Calc. for $C_{14}H_{28}O_2$: C, 73.68; H, 12.28 per cent. M. W., 228.]

The second fraction gave analytical data corresponding to those of palmitic acid. (Found: C, 75.12, 74.93; H, 12.16, 12.63. M. W., 268. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{32}O_2$: C, 75.00; H, 12.50 per cent. M. W. 256).

The mixture, m.p. 48°, contains equal proportions of myristic and palmitic acids (*cf.*, Allen "Commercial Organic Analysis" 1914, II, 385).

Isolation of Viscosin.—The defatted seeds were freed completely from benzene and then extracted exhaustively with boiling ethyl alcohol. The combined alcoholic extracts, on concentration and prolonged standing deposited minute crystals, which were filtered off and washed with benzene. Purification of this substance by recrystallisation gave viscosic acid, m.p. 97°.

The mother-liquor was further concentrated, freed from moisture and extracted with petroleum ether in order to remove oil. The insoluble portion was dissolved in alcohol and the alcoholic solution was treated with an excess of lead acetate. The lead salt was collected and decomposed in alcoholic suspension by sulphuretted hydrogen. Lead sulphide was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated. On dilution with water tannins and a yellow substance were precipitated. The colouring matter was freed from tannins by extracting with boiling water and recrystallising from the same medium for a number of times and finally from aqueous methyl alcohol which deposited pale yellow hexagonal plates. Viscosin was finally crystallised from aqueous isopropyl alcohol. It darkens at 285° and melts with decomposition at 294-95°, yield 1.6 g.

The filtrate from the lead salt of viscosin was freed from lead and concentrated. The residue gave tests for reducing sugars and gave an osazone, m.p. 202°.

Viscosin is easily soluble in ethyl, methyl and isopropyl alcohols, acetone, ethyl acetate, glacial acetic acid, pyridine; less so in chloroform, benzene, nitrobenzene and in hot water; insoluble in petroleum ether, toluene, ether and in cold water. It dissolves in sodium carbonate solution and in caustic alkalis with a bright yellow colour and is precipitated on

acidification. It dissolves in cold concentrated sulphuric acid with a green colour (which turns to orange-yellow on warming), in concentrated nitric acid with red colour and in concentrated hydrochloric acid with a pale yellow colour. With alcoholic ferric chloride it gives a dark green colour and with alcoholic lead acetate a deep yellow precipitate, and a chocolate salt with silver nitrate. The yellow solution of viscosin in warm glacial acetic acid does not change colour on the addition of concentrated sulphuric acid, but becomes greenish-black on the addition of a drop of ferric chloride. It does not reduce Fehling's solution and is non-glucosidic in nature. Treatment of a methyl alcoholic solution with magnesium and hydrochloric acid gives a bright red solution showing that it is a colouring matter of the flavone group. [Found : C, 63.93, 63.87 ; H, 3.90, 4.2 ; OMe, 10.71, 10.56. M. W. (ebullioscopic in methyl alcohol), 312. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64.00 ; H, 4.0, OMe, 10.30 per cent. M. W. 300). No loss of weight occurred when the air-dried sample was heated at 120°.

The *lead salt* is a bright yellow amorphous mass. (Found : Pb, 26.1 ; $C_{32}H_{22}O_{12}Pb$ requires Pb, 25.72 per cent).

The *silver salt*, prepared in the usual manner, was obtained as a chocolate powder. (Found : Ag, 27.24. $C_{16}H_{11}O_6Ag$ requires Ag, 26.49 per cent).

Triacetylviscosin was obtained by acetylating viscosin (1 g.) with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (2 g.) in the usual manner. It forms soft white shining needles, m.p. 222-23°. It is easily soluble in ethyl and methyl alcohol, glacial acetic acid, acetone and ethyl acetate, and insoluble in benzene, petroleum ether, chloroform and water. It gave no colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 62.09 ; H, 4.46. $C_{22}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 61.97 ; H, 4.22 per cent).

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